

#30

Evaluation & Impact Assessment

ACTORS MONITORING DASHBOARD

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>ENGAGING & INCENTIVISING INTERROGATING CREATING ADDRESSING APPLYING</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>Useful during all stages of the initiative, although mostly in the execution and dissemination stage.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Any size. If the initiative has a big network, the tools would be more useful.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>Chart interpretation and basic knowledge on project management.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>Depends on the size of the stakeholder network.</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>Access to a computer, tablet or phone that has MS Office package installed.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tool #4.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Image source: [Roman Synkevych on Unsplash](#)

Purpose

The tool is useful to monitor the actors under various aspects in an integrated way, thanks to the visualization of information. In this way, the managers of innovation initiatives can have under control the progress of the interactions with the different actors in the initiative and generate strategies based on the analysis of the current situation.

This tool pretends to facilitate the visualization of the network status through some parameters that help to analyse how the relationship between the initiative and the actors involved is. It allows one to identify which are the actors closest to the initiative, with whom an interactive work is being done, and with whom, on the contrary, the relationship is weak. Based on this knowledge, the need to improve some connections can be analysed.

Dashboards are commonly used for self-evaluation in project management because it is considered the most efficient way to monitor performance through multiple data sources.

Background Logic

The innovation process is not linear but is considered a complex social system in which different actors participate both formally and informally. In interactive innovation processes, interactions are an aspect that determines the success of initiatives.

In the rural context, the lack of geographical proximity hinders innovation processes, so work must be done to strengthen other aspects that can compensate for or replace geographic isolation. In any case, it is not enough that the actors are close to each other for the innovation process to be carried out successfully, but rather the presence of strong work networks is required for co-design, knowledge transfer, and communication. Dissemination of results. When a network is created around an initiative, its relations need to be monitored to improve them, when necessary, but also to understand how it evolves along with the initiative development and defines plans for future actions.

This tool can be used in conjunction with Tool #4, which can provide a deeper understanding of the satisfaction level of the actors.

Materials

- MS Excel file.

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

This tool integrates data visualization techniques that guide the user's reflection, and dashboard instruments of monitoring. Both aspects allow for the simple analysis of results, facilitating interpretation and decision-making.

What do you need?

How to prepare for it?

To use this tool, it is necessary to have access to a computer, tablet, or phone that has the Office package installed. The Excel file is both the analysis matrix and the template for collecting information. Initial tabs are used to enter the information, while the following are created automatically, allowing the data to be viewed. If the data collection process wants to be done outside the Excel program, it is sufficient to print the first tabs of the Excel. However, to use the visualization system, data entry is required.

Excel Structure

The file has seven tabs, namely: *legend*, *data entry*, *matrix results*, *characterization*, *relationship analysis*, *satisfaction level*, and *participation level*. The first serves as a support material, with the description of the criteria that must be used to assign the values to each actor; the second is where the data are inserted; between the third and seventh tabs, the results obtained are presented automatically from different perspectives.

In the "Data entry" tab, the user will find a table with ten columns, each of which is different information associated with the different actors. The first tab 'Legend' is used as a support to fill the 'Data entry table' because it includes an explanation of the values that must be added to the columns for each actor.

The remaining tabs will be produced autonomously when the data entry process is finished. 'Matrix results', 'Characterization' and 'relationship analysis' are static graphics that visualize information in a general way; on the other hand, 'satisfaction level' and 'participation level' are dynamic graphics that can be analysed through a different range of filters located on the right side of the tab. This system allows for the crossing of different variables that may be useful for interpreting the data and making a more specific decision.

Data Entry

When opening the Excel file, the user must enter the information into the "Data entry" tab. The first column of the table is 'Actor's name'. The step of identifying the actors is crucial: the actors belonging to the network that is interacting with the initiative, or the ones that should be interacting, need to be included in this list. Users can write the name of an institution or person, or even a short description or nickname. The tool does not have predefined information on this aspect, because innovation initiatives are so varied among themselves that there may be a wide range of possibilities to complete the said information. The tool is designed for 30 actors, but there is the option that the user can add others just by including the name at the end of the pre-established space. The table will resize, and the automation will be maintained, although some options will be reduced if the number of actors is more than pre-established.

It is important to identify the relevant actors, and for this reason, some guiding questions are presented below to help identify these actors, but it should be noted that the possibilities are not restricted to the proposed options:

- Who do I get the resources or funding from?
- From whom do I get useful information for initiative?
- Who can I learn from to improve the performance of my initiative?
- Who are my collaborators?
- Who are the end users of the product of innovation?
- Who are my service providers?
- Who are the actors who belong to the supply chain?
- Who can help me ensure the sustainability of the innovation environment generated?
- Who is interested in my field to know about my innovation?
- Who can help and advise me (e.g., universities, public institutions, etc.)?
- Who can help maintain the initiative over time in terms of sustainability?
- Who can help disseminate the results of my innovation to policymakers?
- Which actors help the initiative overcome the social challenges it is addressing?
- Who are my competitors?

LIAISON Tool #30: Actors Monitoring Dashboard

Once the actor identification process is finished and the actors have been listed in the first column 'Actor's name', the user must go to the other columns and complete the information related to each actor: information about 'Type of actor' must be selected from the options available in the tool; the existing 'Type of relationship' for each actor is selected, which can be formal or informal; in the 'Actor location' refers to where the actor is commonly located; Fill in columns 'Type of interaction',

'Level of interaction' and 'Communication type' a value must be selected from those available in the dropdown list and the meaning of each value is explained in detail in the 'Legend' tab; Level of satisfaction, 'Power' and 'Participation' information need to be selected through the dropdown lists that appear in the columns, and the options available in these cases are: very low, low, medium, high and very high.

Actor's name	Type of actor	Type of relationship	Actor's location	Type of Interaction	Level of interaction	Communication type	Satisfaction Level	Power	Participation
Actor 1	Private company	Informal	England	1	3	0	High	High	High
Actor 2	GNO	Informal	Italy	2	3	1	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
Actor 3	GNO	Formal	Madrid, Spain	3	3	2	Low	Low	Low
Actor 4	GNO	Informal	Barcelona, Spain	4	2	1	High	High	High
Actor 5	Individual	Informal	Vigo, Spain	3	1	3			
Actor 6	Individual	Informal	Italy	4	2	2	Low	Low	Low
Actor 7	Private company	Formal	Italy	3	1	3	Low	Low	Low
Actor 8	Academic institution	Formal	Madrid, Spain	2	1	0	Low	Low	Low
Actor 9	Academic institution	Informal	Madrid, Spain	1	2	0	High	High	High
Actor 10	GNO	Formal	Madrid, Spain	2	2	0	High	High	High
Actor 11	Others	Informal	Madrid, Spain	3	4	0	High	High	High
Actor 12	Public institution	Formal	Vigo, Spain	1	4	3	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
Actor 13	Public institution	Informal	Vigo, Spain	1	4	2	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
Actor 14	Public institution	Informal	Barcelona, Spain	1	3	0	Very low	Very low	Very low
Actor 15	GNO	Informal	Barcelona, Spain	2	2	1	Very low	Very low	Very low
Actor 16	GNO	Informal	Barcelona, Spain	2	1	2	Very low	Very low	Very low
Actor 17	Private company	Formal	Vigo, Spain	2	2	1	Very high	Very high	Very high
Actor 18	Private company	Informal	Italy	2	1	3	Very high	Very high	Very high
Actor 19	Others	Informal	Madrid, Spain	2	4	0	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
Actor 20	Public institution	Informal	Barcelona, Spain	1	4	0	Very low	Very low	Very low
Actor 21	GNO	Informal	Barcelona, Spain	3	3	0	Very low	Very low	Very low

Illustration 1. Screenshot of the "Data entry" tab

Some of the information requested about the actors can be provided by the user, but in some cases, the opinion about an actor may not be correct. Regarding this, it is worth mentioning that to have more sources of information to carry out this monitoring exercise, it is possible to apply the survey to the actors involved as much as possible, using the file in Annex 1, called 'Survey to actors'. In addition, if more detail is desired on the parameter 'Satisfaction level', a specific tool is available for that (Satisfaction survey).

In case this is not possible to integrate the information, the tool can work anyway, but it must be considered that all results will be assumptions of the initiative towards the actor, and therefore there will be a different validity of the results, which must be considered when planning strategies. Other ways to determine the indicators are as follows:

- The initiative manager autonomously;
- Through a meeting with the initiative's steering committee;
- Through a participatory workshop with the members of the team and the closest parties.
- The above tools can be integrated to average results.

EXPECTED RESULTS

Once the values have been inserted into the 'Data entry table', the user must go to the other tabs to see the results obtained.

If the results are not displayed automatically, it will be necessary to refresh the data (Select Data > Refresh All).

Matrix Results

In this tab, a matrix is presented where the boxes will change colour depending on the value assigned to each item, showing the results visually. This so that a detailed or general visualization of all aspects and all actors can be made. The topics are arranged in a matrix format, where both actors and variables are interrelated. For a more in-depth analysis, the general status of the interaction with a particular actor can be visually evaluated by analysing the matrix horizontally; to make a general consideration about the variables throughout the actors, the matrix can be analysed vertically. In this visualization, the results are interpreted according to a colour code described in the legend on the right side of the tab. The aspects in red are those that have been evaluated negatively; therefore, if the context requires it, actions should be taken to improve each aspect for a specific actor.

Matrix Results				
Actor's name	Type of Interaction	Level of interaction	Communication type	Participation
Actor 1	3	0	High	High
Actor 2	3	1	Moderate	Moderate
Actor 3	3	2	Low	Low
Actor 4	2	1	High	High
Actor 5	1	3	High	Moderate
Actor 6	2	2	High	Low
Actor 7	1	3	Moderate	High
Actor 8	1	0	Moderate	High
Actor 9	2	0	Very low	High
Actor 10	2	0	High	Moderate
Actor 11	4	0	High	Moderate
Actor 12	4	3	Moderate	Very low
Actor 13	4	2	Moderate	Moderate
Actor 14	3	0	Very low	Very low
Actor 15	2	1	Very low	Very low
Actor 16	1	2	Very low	Very low
Actor 17	2	1	Very high	Very high
Actor 18	1	3	Very high	Moderate
Actor 19	4	0	Moderate	Moderate
Actor 20	4	0	Moderate	Very low
Actor 21	5	0	Very low	High
Actor 22	5	0	High	High
Actor 23	2	3	High	Moderate

	Very Bad
	Bad
	Intermediate
	High
	Very high

Legend | Data entry | **Matrix results** | Characterization | Relationship analysis | Satisfaction level | Participation level

Illustration 2. Screenshot of the tab 'Matrix results'

Characterization

In this tab, there is a dashboard with the characterization of the actors that are forming the network. From the graphs, the typologies of the actors and their diversity or homogeneity can be easily visualized. It is a dashboard that characterizes the actors who were identified through the basic information assigned. This information is useful to

analyse the variability of actors and compare it with what was planned or estimated during the planning phase. If the deviations are high or the initiative neglects potentially relevant stakeholder typologies, this will be visualized, and decisions can be made to improve it.

Illustration 3. Screenshot of the tab 'Characterization'

In this tab, a single scatter plot is displayed. This graph shows the results of the distribution of the different actors according to their type of communication and level of interaction. These variables, which have been indicated in the input data table, are information that gives an approximate indication of the quality of the relationship that exists between the initiative and a given actor. This graph must be interpreted based on the knowledge of the initiative manager in each of the specific cases, but, as a general indication, the colour code that appears can be used. Based on where the actor is placed on the graph, it will have a related colour, which indicates the quality of the relationship. Important to highlight is the grey colour, where

all those actors that could currently be considered outside the network are located but that have been named as potentially relevant actors. If the data are updated over time, it is possible to obtain a temporal sequence of the inclusion of actors within the network, as well as to see the evolution of the relationships between the actors and the initiative.

If the names of the actors overlap, it is possible to move them to better appreciate the results, dragging them to a more visible place on the graph. The grey line that detaches from each circle should always be considered to have more clarity about the location of the actor in the graph.

Illustration 4. Screenshot of the tab 'Relationship analysis'

Satisfaction Level

The graph shown in this tab shows the distribution of the level of satisfaction through the different actors. It can be interpreted using the filters on the right. The filters that are applied will modify the results of the graph showing only those that the user wants to analyse. The filter function is very useful to cross information from different actors to

analyse a specific situation. For example, to know the level of satisfaction of those actors who have a high power/ influence on the initiative but only those who belong to the interaction type of the funders, it would be necessary to select the corresponding filters, and the graph would modify automatically.

 To remove all filters, you must press this button in each filter category.

Illustration 5. Screenshot of the tab 'Satisfaction level'

Participation Level

Its operation is like that presented in the tab "Satisfaction level", but in this case, it is allowed to

analyse the level of participation of all actors by subdividing them, according to what is required to be analysed through the filters placed on the right.

Illustration 6. Screenshot of the tab "Participation level"

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